

Workplace Violence and Associated Factors Among Healthcare Professionals Working at Public Hospitals in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: A Cross-Sectional Study

Bemnet Fekre (MD, MPH)¹, Natnael Atle Benti (MD, MPH)², Bethelhem Tamiru Tasew (MD, MPH)³, Bemnet Yacobe Sayid (MD, MPH)⁴, Huda Mohammed Fetwi (MD)⁵

¹ Department of General surgery, Eka kotebe General Hospital, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

² Department of Emergency and Critical care, St. Peter's Specialized Hospital, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

³ Quality Director, Aabet Hospital, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

⁴ Department of Gynecology, Eka kotebe General Hospital, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

⁵ Department of Pediatrics, Alert Comprehensive Specialized Hospital, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

*Correspondence: bemnetfekre@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Background: Workplace violence has emerged as a global problem that affects all nations, workplaces, and occupational categories. The health sector accounts for more than one-third of all workplace violence worldwide. There is very little information available in Ethiopia about workplace violence affecting healthcare professionals. This study aims to shed light on the issue by gaining a better understanding of the problem and developing a targeted intervention. Therefore, the objective of the study was to assess the prevalence of workplace violence and associated factors among healthcare professionals working in selected public hospitals in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

Methods: An analytic cross-sectional study was conducted from May 1- June 30, 2023 among 599 randomly selected healthcare professionals working at four randomly selected referral hospitals in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. Data was collected using a pretested structured self-administered questionnaire adapted from the ILO/ICN/WHO/PSI^a. The data were coded and entered to EPI information version 7 and exported to SPSS V.20.0 software for analysis. Frequency table was used to summarize data. To identify factors associated with workplace violence, a binary logistic regression model where the degree of association for variables was assessed using adjusted odds ratios (AOR) with 95% CI and p-value ≤ 0.05

Results: The prevalence of experiencing at least one type of workplace violence (physical, verbal, bullying, or sexual) in the previous year was found to be 59.4% (95% CI = 55.6–63.1). The study revealed a statistically significant relationship between workplace violence and female sex (AOR=1.56, 95% CI=1.04-2.34, p=0.033), pharmacist profession (AOR=2.9, 95% CI=1.15-7.33, p=0.025), routine direct physical contact with patients (AOR=2.19, 95% CI=1.12-4.29, p=0.022), emergency work starting (AOR=2.50, 95% CI=1.02-6.15, p=0.045), and witnessing incidents of physical violence (AOR=10.1, 95% CI=5.75-17.59, p<0.0001).

Conclusions: The study found a high prevalence of workplace violence among health care professionals working in government hospitals in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. Healthcare facilities should prioritize the establishment of comprehensive health and safety programs focusing on the prevention and management of workplace violence, with particular attention to the most vulnerable groups.

Key words: Workplace violence, Healthcare professionals, cross-sectional study, Public Hospitals, Binary logistic regression, Ethiopia.

^a The International Labour Office, International Council of Nurses, World Health Organization and Public Services International

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